

Accessible, Diverse, and Colourful: Applying 3D Tech and Pop Art Vocab to the Roman Imperial Image

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The gift shops at the Colosseum and the Ara Pacis in Rome offer an enticing and colourful array of four light-weight and ornamental portrait heads of Roman imperial family members in different textures and sizes (below and page 26 and 30). The effect for those over the age of fifty is an engaging three-dimensional pop art, an Andy Warhol of repeating heads of an emperor. For the younger crowd accustomed to 3D scans, virtual reality, and MeshLab, the most striking detail is that these heads are not rotating on a screen. They really are on the shelf, and you can turn them in your hand, even noting poorly scanned areas under the chin. No one in the shops, however, seems to know exactly what they are – what or where are the originals and why they should be purchased at prices that range from 45 to 450 euros. Putting these portraits of Roman emperors in context – historic, academic, and modern – allows us to reflect on the evolution of the modes and reasons for reproductions of the Roman Emperor.

The most obvious and ubiquitous of the heads is that of Augustus. Suitably an array of large heads of Augustus in different textures fills the window of the museum shop at the Ara Pacis or Altar of Peace (below). Outside the window, behind the display, the modern tourist sees the ruins of Augustus' massive mausoleum, a man-made mound constructed in 28 BC with trees on top

and a *dromos* (entrance tunnel) flanked by two obelisks (now still integral to the city's fabric at Santa Maria Maggiore and on the Quirinal Hill). In conjunction with his impressive Mausoleum, Augustus had built a large clock, *horologium*, and the Altar of Peace; a grand political gesture connecting himself eternally with peace. In 1937 Benito Mussolini sponsored the hi-tech excavation of the altar. Pieces of it had been found already in the sixteenth century but attempts to extract it from wet soil beneath Palazzo Peretti had been in vain until the fascist regime applied modern science to freeze the ground in 1937–1938. Mussolini commissioned a careful display case for the freshly excavated monument and inscribed Augustus' last will and testament in bronze letters on its base. The building formed one side of a new rationalist square, completed in 1938, around the Mausoleum. Only in 1999 did the city of Rome commission the architect Richard Meyer to build a more permanent museum (completed in 2006). These few facts suffice to show the extremely political nature of the setting and the long-standing importance of Augustus in it.

Included in the Ara Pacis Museum shop display are reproductions of a nineteenth century engraving of a statue which is crucial for our understanding of the head (page 26, below). The statue, now in the Braccio Nuovo

Display of heads of Augustus on sale at the Ara Pacis Museum Shop, with the Mausoleum of Augustus outside the window.

Heads of Augustus on sale at the Colosseum Gift Shop for 45 euros.

of the Vatican Museums, is the most iconic image of a Roman emperor known today; a 6.1m copy of it defines Caesar's Palace (1966) in Las Vegas (page 27, left). Excavated at the Villa of Livia at Prima Porta, ancient Saxa Rubra, nine miles north of Rome in 1863, the statue shows Augustus in parade armour. On his breast plate is a complicated narrative of his reign that combines cosmic allegories and historic facts. The statue moreover preserves traces of colour and a well-preserved head; academic plaster reproductions show both of these well (page 27, right). The ancient sculptors made the head separate from the statue

and inserted it into a cavity at the neck. Modern and ancient viewers would never have noticed this.

The portrait head gives its name, the 'Prima Porta' type, to a model which the ancient Romans disseminated throughout their world in massive numbers to establish cohesion and unity among the various constituents of the Empire. Artisans reproduced it faithfully in different media and at different scales from tiny gems for an elite few to thousands of coins for the entire populace and in honorific statues which appeared at colossal scale in temples and in life or just over life-size in public

Heads of Augustus with prints of statue of Augustus of Prima Porta, Ara Pacis Museum Shop.

A gilt version of Augustus Prima Porta in Caesar's Palace.

squares. Preserved in more copies (around 150) than any other ancient portrait, the model was designed to exude composure, confidence, sobriety, and to convey an ageless and timeless quality. How the Roman artisans transmitted the image created in the capital city for its first Emperor to all the various artists throughout the Empire remains unclear. They may have distributed two dimensional drawings or three-dimensional plaster or clay models. The ancient version on which the museum shop heads are based is actually not that of the Prima Porta statue but rather of a head found in Centuripe, Sicily (page 28, below left). That this portrait head, a replica already in antiquity, is now again available in different colours, finishes, and sizes in the gift job is perfectly in keeping with its original intent and accessibility. The design continues to maintain its appeal and evoke the authority of Augustus' new age of peace and prosperity.

The modern versions add to our knowledge both of the original object and of the motivations for copying. The museum shop versions allow us to see the ancient portrait as a head, separate from the statue. We can see the unfinished back of the neck and the inclusion of right clavicle (page 28, above left) which allowed the turned head to be fitted snugly against the clothing, probably armour, of its statue and appreciate fully the practicality of the ancient marble sculpture business. This brings to our attention that the modern makers conceived their portrait as a stand-alone object which needs no body to

convey its message. Conceptually their idea is that of an ancient portrait bust (page 28, below) rather than a head set on a statue. A second and equally interesting reflection concerns the transfer of the design to the product. Although, as noted above, we do not know how this was done in antiquity, here a 3D scan of the head of Centuripe allows for 3D printing. Like their ancient predecessors, the modern makers are producers of a prefabricated image which they are confident will sell, and they allow the consumers to make choices about colours and textures in accordance with taste and budget. Compare for instance the green metallic-looking bust of Germanicus of c. AD 15–25 (page 28, below right), an expensive item because of the difficulties involved with carving the very hard basanite stone quarried in Egypt. The lack of manual input in today's world corresponds to a lack of signed imperial images in antiquity. No individual ancient sculptor ever took credit for making such an object.

This 3D printed Augustus prepares us for three further heads on sale at the Colosseum shop. There we find a middle-aged man with a slim face and lank hair (page 29, above), a full-faced man with a big nose, receding chin and a curled fringe (page 30, above), and

Painted plaster Augustus Prima Porta in the Ashmolean Museum.

young woman with styled hair and a crown (page 29, below). These carry the labels, Caesar, Antonia, and Titus. In 2003, a combined German and Italian archaeological team excavated the Roman-period marble versions of these three heads on the island of Pantelleria off the west coast of Sicily, ancient Cossyra (page 30, below). All three were made separately from their statue bodies and had tenons of varying size at the bottom of their necks so that they could be inserted into statues. The largest of the heads, that of Titus, lay amid refuse of the fifth to sixth century AD in a cistern. Scholars hypothesise that he had been removed

from his statue and deposited there by invading Vandals in the 460s. The other two heads were found in a second cistern below a layer of animal bones and ceramics dated to the later first century AD, which suggests that they were placed before AD 75. Whoever these two were intended to be, the people of Cossyra no longer wanted them on their statues very shortly after they had been erected.

These offerings provide today's tourist with a versatile, if not broad, range of gender and ages from which to choose. The terse labels and bright colours once again effectively separate the original marbles found at Pantelleria from the twenty-first century product. We are to understand these as modern versions of the named historic personages. The new heads of Titus are cut evenly through the neck, highlighting that this is not a replica or even a full print of the Pantelleria marble but simply a version of Titus.

Yet whereas this works seamlessly for Titus as it did for Augustus, both of whom were emperors, it glosses over the problematic identification of the other two heads, the two that the Cossyrans got rid of as early as the later first century. The application of the name Caesar to the lank-haired man with the straight nose seems convincing to us and may even have seemed so to the ancients. The profile of Caesar appeared on ancient coins, so we know, as did they, that he had a slim face, a receding hair line, and a wrinkled neck. Yet the large-scale system of distributing a designed model of the emperor for reproduction in all parts of the Empire began only with the first Roman Emperor, Augustus. It post-dates Julius Caesar. Furthermore, sculptures of Caesar were made posthumously and without invested political interest or in conjunction with later family members. Augustus, especially in his later years, downplayed his connection to Caesar and his links to the last years of vicious civil war and infighting amongst

Above: profile view of a mint green 3D digital print which shows the unworked area at the back of the neck.

Right: portrait head of Augustus, 27 BC–AD 14. Marble. Height: 28cm (head). Museo Archeologico, Centuripe, inv. 50698.

Far right: bust of Germanicus. AD 14–20. Green basanite. Height: 47cm. The British Museum, inv. 1872,0605.1.

Head of Caesar, white (320 euros), and head of Augustus, black,(420 euros) on the same shelf at the Colosseum Gift Shop.

the Roman elite. Thus, a portrait of a lean-faced, fifty-year-old man with thinning hair without an identifying inscription might well be Caesar but might equally well *not* be Caesar. The Pantelleria portrait head loosely resembles three portraits identified by modern scholars as Caesar: a portrait head from Tusculum (now in Turin), a portrait head in the Vatican Chiaramonti collection, and a bust found in the Rhone river, near Arles, in 2007. None of these heads however repeat the same model with the consistency of the portraits of the Roman emperors from Augustus onwards. Moreover, it is hard to understand

why the Cossyrans would wish to rid themselves of such a handsome and well-made marble portrait of a man long dead, dead even before the head was commissioned.

His Pantelleria companion, the portrait sold as Antonia, is equally problematic (page 31, left). The woman wears a crown and a beaded woollen band in her hair, both of which indicate her imperial status. In contrast to Caesar but like Augustus and Titus, there are other extant, ancient versions of the model on which the Pantelleria head was based. Whereas there are almost 150 extant versions of the Augustus Prima Porta model, there are a total of only

Head of Antonia in glossy olive at the Colosseum Gift Shop.

Heads of Titus in pastel colours (45 euros) at the Colosseum Gift Shop.

five preserved versions of this female model: the one from Pantelleria, fragments from Lanuvium (outside of Rome) and from Narona in modern Croatia, a restored head in the Torlonia collection in Rome, and one now in New York. The American collector Archer Milton Huntington purchased this latter-most head in 1905 in southern Spain for the Hispanic Society of America, as testimony of Spain's participation in the Roman Empire (page 31, right). A comparison between it and the Pantelleria head illustrates the minor and inadvertent differences that emerge when two sculptors, working from the same model, created

similarly-sized heads for insertion into almost standard statues at more or less the same moment.

The physiognomy and hairstyle of the princess recalls aspects of the well-identified portraits of members of the Julio-Claudian family – famous in antiquity and brought to life by Robert Graves' novel, *I, Claudius*. These are Antonia the Younger (daughter of Mark Antony and Octavia, mother of the Emperor Claudius), Agrippina the Elder (daughter of Agrippa and Julia, mother of the Emperor Caligula and Agrippina the Younger), and Agrippina the Younger (daughter of Agrippina and Germanicus). All

Three portrait heads found at Pantelleria off the west coast of Sicily (ancient Cossyra).
 Left: 'Antonia';
 centre: Titus Pantelleria;
 right: 'Caesar'.
 First century AD. Marble.
 Height: 42.5cm;
 45cm; 42cm.
 right: 'Caesar'. Marble.
 Museo Archeologico,
 Castello di Pantelleria,
 inv. 4644; inv. 5857;
 inv. 4643.

Portrait head of a princess from Pantelleria.
Museo Archeologico, Castello di Pantelleria
(also illustrated on page 28, left).

Portrait head of the same princess purchased in Spain in 1905.
First century AD. Marble. Height: 37.5cm.
Hispanic Society of America, inv. D 203.

of these women and several others – for example, the cousins and the sisters of Agrippina the Younger – were related by birth and marriage, grew up and matured in the public eye, and had moments of prominence. The true appearance of these numerous women of the imperial house in the Julio-Claudian period could not have been well-known outside of the city of Rome. In the first half of the first century AD the peripheral members of the imperial family, male and female, appeared only occasionally on coins. Family resemblances and shared roles required that public statues of these individuals stand on bases inscribed with their names, otherwise they would not be recognized. Surely the Pantelleria portrait represented one of the princesses but, as with the portrait of ‘Caesar’, we must ask why the Cossyrans dumped her portrait head into a cistern, rather than simply change the label on the base beneath or adjust her physiognomy for a new honorand. A few of the imperial women, in the years between AD 20–50, were accused of political crimes and ended their lives in disgrace. Most prominent of these was Livilla, the daughter of Antonia, sister of the emperor Claudius, wife to Gaius and then Drusus Caesar. She infamously had a love affair with the Prefect of the Praetorian Guard Sejanus and plotted against her husband and her nephews.

It is interesting to note that the New York version of the princess, like the Pantelleria one, is also getting digital attention in a museum setting. The Curator of Sculpture at the Hispanic Society, Patrick Lenaghan,

and the Curator of the Fordham Art Museum, Jennifer Udell, are seeking to reassemble the full statue of the princess which the original workshop made in three major pieces of marble – lower body, upper body, and head to be inserted into a socket – by means of 3D scans of the archaeological parts which have lost structural integrity and are difficult to manoeuvre. That heads of the same princess are being reproduced in digital versions for different audiences reflects our new tool box but not a different concept.

Whoever they might have been made to represent in the first century, the new heads in the twenty-first century museum shops of Rome have clear identities – Augustus, Titus, Caesar, and Antonia. They show us a surprising continuity in intent of design, mass production, and public consumption. This last point is perhaps the most illuminating since we see economics and personal choice at play and the possibility that new labels can change old identities. They give us new technologies and new media but surprisingly also betray a constant desire for these personable-looking individuals who ruled the Roman Empire.

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RESP has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant G.A. 101002763).